

Bio-Psycho-Social Correlates of Psychological Disorders and Coping Styles among Indian Children and Adolescents: A Cross-sectional Study

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Adolescence is a vulnerable phase of life in which emotional and physical developmental changes impact the thinking and perception of the individual. This study aims to analyze the frequency pattern among psychological disorders, coping styles, and bio-psycho-social contributing factors among clinically referred Indian children and adolescents. The study was conducted on 515 individuals aged 8-18 years through a cross-sectional descriptive design. Detailed clinical interview and MSE were done and a psychological assessment was conducted using DSM-5 Cross-Cutting Symptom Measures (APA, 2022) and the Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations-21 (Endler & Parker, 1990). Results shows that frequency of depressive disorders and anxiety disorders were the most prevalent conditions followed by somatoform and OCD in young adolescents, maladaptive coping were used by children's with mental health disorders, only 8 percent sample population exhibit adaptive coping, Social and environmental stressors were dominant triggers of psychological issues in children followed by psychological and biological factors, it is also seen that some of the individual showed mixed trigger of their mental health. The findings highlight the importance of early psychological screening, school mental health programs, family interventions, and integrated bio-psycho-social approaches for improving child and adolescent mental health outcomes in India.

Keywords: Children's mental health, psychopathology, bio-psycho-social model, coping style, adolescence

India hosts the largest child and adolescent population globally, comprising over 434 million individuals under the age of 18 years (UNICEF, 2024). Nearly one in five people in India is an adolescent aged 10 to 19 years (Census of India 2011). Emotional development during childhood and adolescence is a multifaceted process influenced by the dynamic interaction between biological/biochemical and environmental experiences (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Casey et al., 2008). Children and adolescents represent a particularly vulnerable population with emotional, behavioral and cognitive development (Steinberg, 2014; World Health Organization, 2020). Recent epidemiological studies have increasingly highlighted the increasing burden of child and adolescent mental health disorders globally (World Health Organization, 2020). It has been estimated that approximately 50% of mental health disorders begin before the age of 14 years (Kessler et al., 2005; World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). During this phase, young individuals develop thinking, perceptions, Ego consciousness, problem solving, decision

making and coping mechanisms. The prefrontal cortex was not fully developed at this age and it can impact emotional regulation, making them highly vulnerable to psychological and environmental influences (Casey et al., 2008; Steinberg, 2014).

The Bio-Psycho-Social Model of Child Mental Health

Biological factors significantly contribute to the development of psychological and psychiatric disorders among children and adolescents (Nkuba et al., 2018). Family and twin studies have demonstrated substantial heritability for several psychiatric conditions (Faraone et al., 2005; Plomin et al., 2016; Thapar et al., 2013). Neurodevelopment disorder like attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) have an estimated heritability of approximately 74%, indicating a strong genetic contribution (Faraone et al., 2005; Thapar et al., 2013). Research on heritability demonstrates that genes significantly contribute to the differences in intelligence, personality, and vulnerability to mental disorders and gene-environment interactions influence brain development and neurotransmitter functions (Plomin et al., 2016; Thapar et al., 2013). During childhood and adolescence, there are critical structural and functional changes in the brain. The prefrontal cortex (PFC), which is essential for executive functions such as decision-making, impulse control, and reasoning, continues to develop until early adulthood, whereas the limbic system, including the amygdala, is particularly active during adolescence and is key to emotional processing (Casey et al., 2008; Steinberg, 2010).

Neurotransmitters such as dopamine, serotonin, and norepinephrine are essential for regulating mood, attention, and behavior. Dysregulation of neurotransmitters has been linked to various psychological disorders, including depression, anxiety disorders, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (American

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Psychiatric Association [APA], 2022). The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is crucial for managing the stress response (McEwen, 2007; Meaney, 2010). Long-term or ongoing stress can impair the functioning of the HPA axis, raising the risk for anxiety and depression (McEwen, 2007). Furthermore, the heightened neural plasticity seen in childhood and adolescence facilitates learning and adaptation but also makes individuals more vulnerable to negative environmental influences, highlighting the need for early supportive measures (Kolb & Gibb, 2011). Chronic Health Conditions: Physical illnesses like diabetes, epilepsy, or chronic pain can trigger or worsen mental health conditions in adults (CDC, 2025).

Environmental and Social Factors

Environmental and social factors substantially influence the psychological well-being of children and adolescents. Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) such as physical /verbal or sexual abuse, parental neglect, family conflict, bullying, parental separation, and low academic performance have consistently been associated with an increased risk of emotional and behavioral disorders (Shonkoff et al., 2012). Family environment, parenting practices, socio-economic adversity, and peer relationships/ peer rejection and social media comparison significantly contribute to emotional adjustment during childhood and adolescence (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Furthermore, school-related stressors including examination and academic pressure, fear of failure, competition, parental comparison and expectation have been identified as major contributors to anxiety and depressive symptoms among Indian adolescents (Deb et al., 2015). Recent literature has additionally highlighted that the role of excessive social media/ screen use, cyberbullying, and problematic internet engagement is increasing insecurities in children, resulting in distress and poor psychological well-being among children and adolescents (Odgers & Jensen, 2020; World Health Organization, 2020).

Psychological Factors

Psychological factors distorted cognitive functioning, resulting in low self-esteem, perfectionism, emotional deregulation, negative self-perception, unusual expectations from others and maladaptive coping styles, which may increase susceptibility to psychological disorders among adolescents (Harter, 2012). Exposure to traumatic experiences including any type of abuse, accidents, bereavement, and interpersonal conflict may further impair emotional regulation and coping abilities and development of personality traits, existing studies have also demonstrated that children with chronic medical conditions (cancer/ juvenile diabetes) or learning difficulties experience elevated psychological distress due to academic challenges, physical pain, social stigma, and reduced emotional support (Pinquart & Shen, 2011).

Need for the Study

Despite the growing recognition of childhood mental health concerns, substantial gaps persist in research on the frequency of psychological disorders, coping style among children and adolescents with psychiatric disorders. Similarly, very limited data is available on the role of biological psychological and environmental interaction on mental health, particularly within the Indian context and more specifically in the state of Haryana.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to examine the distribution of psychological disorders, the contribution of social, biological and psychological factors and coping style among clinically referred children and to explore the association between disorder categories and bio-psychosocial contributing factors.

Method

Participants

The study sample consisted of 515 clinically referred children and adolescents ($N = 515$) aged between 8 to 18 years ($M = 14.46$, $SD = 2.06$), selected through purposive sampling. The sample included 259 males (50.8%) and 256 females (49.2%).

Inclusion criteria included 1, children and adolescents aged 8-18 years, (2) presence of psychological or emotional difficulties identified during clinical assessment, and (3) parental consent for participation. Exclusion criteria included: (1) severe psychiatric disturbances, (2) diagnosed neurodevelopment disorders, and (3) unwillingness to participate in the study.

Research Design

The present study follows a cross-sectional descriptive-correlation research. This design allows for detailed exploration of the relationship between mental health and its causes and coping strategies in children with mental health issues. These children aged 8-18 years were selected through probability cluster sampling from government and private hospitals and clinics in Haryana. Those who scored above the threshold for mental health issues during preliminary screening were further assessed for severity, triggers, and coping styles.

Measures

The independent variables included gender, socio-economic status and biological, psychological, and socio-environmental contributing factors, along with coping styles. The primary outcome variable was the category of psychological disorder identified during assessment.

Coping styles were assessed using the Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations-21 (Endler & Parker, 1990), The CISS-21 is a standard self report measure consist of 21 items, which measures three domains of coping emotional coping, avoidance coping, and problem-solving coping styles Participants respond on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Not at all") to 5 ("Very much"). Higher scores indicate greater use of a particular coping strategy. The CISS-21 has demonstrated satisfactory reliability and validity in adolescent populations. Internal consistency in the present study was within an acceptable range (Cronbach's $\alpha > .70$).

To evaluate emotional and behavioral symptoms in children and adolescents, the DSM-5 Cross-Cutting Symptom Measure (CCSM) and the respective PROMIS Level 2 Pediatric Scales were used with 7-11-year and 11-17-year age groups, respectively. The Child Self-Rated DSM-5 Level 1 CCSM at ages of 11-17 years includes 25 items to assess 12 major symptom domains, although parent-reported versions of the CCSM and PROMIS pediatric scales are more acceptable in younger children (ages 7-11 years) because of developmental constraints in self-report accuracy. When a child's Level 1 CCSM score exceeds the clinical threshold in any domain, the study administers the PROMIS Level 2 measures. The PROMIS

Pediatric Depression Scale reports a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93. Convergent validity has been established, with the PROMIS Depression scale correlating at $r = .71$.

A semi-structured clinical history format was additionally used to obtain detailed birth history, history of present illness and current stressors and precipitation factors, developmental, psychosocial, familial, and behavioral information.

Procedure

Data were collected through individual clinical interviews through semi-structured history and MSE format, psychological screening was conducted to screen the type of disorder by using DSM- 5 self-report symptom measures and coping styles were assessed using the CISS-21 questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics Software 26.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize demographic variables and disorder categories. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictive contribution of biological, psychological, and social factors on disorder severity. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

Results

The current study involves 515 participants from 8-18 years with equal distribution of gender, majority of participants scored high for depressive disorder ($N=116$) with almost equal distribution in both gender, with significantly higher rates of anxiety spectrum ($N=93$) in females (22.66%) as compared to male (13.51%), OCD ($N=41$) is also slightly higher in females(8.20%) as compared to males(7.72%) similarly with somatic symptoms ($N= 48$) among female participants (10.54%) as compared to males (7.72%), females also score high personality traits. Male participants show predominance in "externalizing" behaviors like behaviour n conduct issues (14.67%) in contrast to females (5.47). The data also shows that male participants show higher prevalence in substance abuse and addiction (8.11%)(Table-1)

Analyses of Coping style show that (242) 46.99 % participants show Emotional Coping, followed by (228) 44.27% participants

with Avoidance Coping and a few participants (45)8.74 % showed Problem Solving Coping mechanism revealed that mental health impacts problem-solving capacity in children (Table 2).

The data also revealed that (253) 48.93% of participants experienced distress mainly associated with social or environmental triggers. The disorders that are associated with environmental stressors are family conflict, academic pressure, and relationship challenges. Followed by 134 participants (26.02%) who exhibit psychological factors accounting for their mental health issues. 105 (20.39%) participants have biological factors behind their psychological issues, 22 participants (4.27%) exhibit mixed social and psychological causes, and 1 participant has mixed biological and social causes (Table 3).

The age-wise distribution of the bio-psycho-social domain and common diagnoses shows majority of the participants from the age group 4-10 years were represented by biological causes (family history), and the common diagnoses were school anxiety, adjustment issues, and somatic complaints, with a mean disorder score of 37.24. Participants aged between 11 to 13 years show a dominant causative domain as social, disorders are depressive disorders, majorly with a Mean disorder score of 32.87. Participants aged 14 to 16 years mostly show mixed environmental and psychological causes. With disorders mean score of 41.50. Participants aged 17 to 18 years have social and psychological causes with major disorders such as depression, bipolar disorder, OCD, and panic attacks, with a mean disorder score of 38.73. It shows that the older adolescents are more exposed to chronic environmental stressors with peak academic stress, and across all the cases, the major domain of causes will be psychological as well as environmental (Table 3.1).

Regression analysis revealed that psychological factors were a high predictor of overall disorder severity ($\beta = .36, p < .001$), despite social/environmental factors being the most commonly cited causes of mental health problems among children and adolescents (48.93%). This implies that psychological vulnerabilities may have a greater impact on the severity and clinical appearance of mental health illnesses, even while environmental challenges are very common. Within the biopsychosocial paradigm, biological factors also significantly predicted the severity of the disease, demonstrating the multifaceted character of childhood psychopathology.

Table 1
Gender-wise Distribution of Frequency of Mental Health Disorders

Disorder	Female (n)	Male(n)	Total (N)
Depressive Disorders	59(23.05%)	57(22.01%)	116
Anxiety Spectrum Disorders	58(22.66%)	35(13.51%)	93
Obsessive-Compulsive and Related Disorders (OCD)	21(8.20%)	20(7.72%)	41
Psychotic Disorders	19(7.42%)	24(9.27%)	43
Behavioral and Conduct Disorders	14(5.47%)	38(14.67%)	52
Somatic and Psychosomatic Disorders	28(10.54%)	20(7.72%)	48
Dissociative and Related Disorders	13(5.08%)	8(3.095%)	21
Mood Disorders (Bipolar / Mania / Hypomania)	15(5.86%)	14(5.14%)	29
Addiction and Substance Use Disorders	5(1.95%)	21(8.11%)	26
Personality and Adjustment Disorders	16(6.25%)	14(5.41%)	30
BDD	4(1.56%)	6(2.23%)	10
Others (Low Frequency)	4(1.56%)	2(0.77%)	6

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Coping Mechanisms (N = 515)

Coping Mechanism	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Emotional coping	242	46.99
Avoidance coping	228	44.27
Problem-solving coping	45	8.74
Total	515	100.00

Table 3
Bio /Psycho/Social Causes of Mental Health

Domain	N	%	Common Disorders
Social (Environmental)	253	48.93	Depression, Anxiety, Behavioral Problems
Psychological	134	26.02	Depression, Anxiety, PTSD, Somatoform
Biological	105	20.39	OCD, Bipolar, Conduct, Psychosis
Social + Psychological	22	4.27	Exam Anxiety, Adjustment, Somatoform
Social + Biological	1	0.19	Schizophrenia, Bipolar Mood Disorder
Total	515	100	

Table 3.1
Age Wise Distribution of Causative Factors (Bio-Psycho-Social)

AgeGroup (Years)	N (Participants)	Dominant Cause Type	Common Diagnoses
4-10 (Childhood)	51	Biological	School anxiety, adjustment, somatic complaints
11-13(Early Adolescence)	94	Social	Depressive Disorder
14-16 (Mid Adolescence)	187	Psychological / Mixed (Psycho-Social)	Depression, exam anxiety, OCD, dissociative symptoms
17-18 (Late Adolescence / Early Adulthood)	183	Social+ Psychological	Depression, bipolar mood, OCD, panic attacks
Overall (4-18 years)	515	Psychological+ Social	Depression, anxiety, somatic symptoms

Table 4
Regression Analyses for Prediction of Mental Health as Per Causes

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
(Constant)	9.82	2.11	-	4.65	.000
Biological Severity	0.31	0.06	.22	5.17	.000
Psychological Severity	0.45	0.05	.36	8.94	.000
Social Severity	0.28	0.07	.18	4.02	.000

Note. All predictors were statistically significant at $p < .001$. Statistical significance level was set at $p < .05$

Discussion

The study looked at how often psychological disorders show up along with coping style and bio-psycho- social factors in a group of 515 children and teens from clinical settings, specifically in the social culture context of Haryana in India. The result showed that emotional and avoidance coping strategies were the go-to method for most people, while environmental and social factors stood out as the biggest drivers behind these disorders.

The present study reported the predominance of environmental and social causes, which accounted for 48% of participants. These findings strongly align with Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1979) which proposes that child development and psychological functioning are profoundly shaped by interactions

within family, school, peer, and societal environments. Participants in the present study frequently reported bullying, parental conflict, abusive parenting, academic stress, bereavement, peer pressure, and social rejection as major contributing stressors. Similar findings have been reported in Indian and international literature, where adverse childhood experiences and dysfunctional family environments were found to significantly predict anxiety, depression, behavioral disturbances, and psychosomatic symptoms among adolescents (Shonkoff et al., 2012; Patel et al., 2018). Family-related adversities represented a major category of environmental causes in children from 8 to 18 years identified in the study. Parental conflict, neglectful parenting, authoritarian discipline, emotional unavailability, and family instability were frequently associated with psychological symptoms among participants. These findings are congruent with Baumrind's (1991) parenting framework and attachment-based theories, which suggest that harsh and emotionally inconsistent parenting environments negatively affect emotional regulation, attachment security, and behavioral adjustment. Previous Indian studies have similarly reported that adolescents exposed to chronic family stress and low emotional support exhibit significantly greater emotional and behavioral disturbances (Deb et al., 2015).

Pressure and stress within the academy and its school life emerged as a key factor, and were particularly detrimental for children aged 13 and 14. A lot was written about exam jitters, fear of not doing

well at exams, anxiety about doing well at exams and pressures to achieve top marks by children in the study. There is even more logic in the school world of India, as doing well academically is not only about grades. It's a matter of pride, social status and hope for a better tomorrow. The findings correlate with Deb et al. (2015) who found that academic stress causes anxiety and depression, sleep issues and suicidal ideation in teenagers from India. Added to this, local culture in Haryana appears to push the envelope on the mental health impacts on young people, with "dummy schools" and exam rivalry among schools also coming into the picture, along with pressure on the honor of the family. Anxiety and depression were also the most prevalent mental health concerns within our group, with findings similar to larger-scale research, which revealed them as the most prevalent mental health issues across teens (Merikangas et al., 2009; Polanczyk et al., 2005).

This work also provided insights into children and young people's coping responses to stress and emotional fluctuations for everyday living. Emotional coping was their favorite response (46.99%), followed by avoidance coping (44.27%). An extremely small percentage went for the problem-solving approaches (8.74%). A general impression was that most young people did not seem to track stress, but rather took raw emotion when the stress hit them, or ignored the stress entirely. There were common themes of fear, helplessness, frustration and 'going numb' when approached by something difficult. Very few actually retired for a practical meet-the-problem discussion and attempted to put proposed solutions into practice. These habits can, over time, affect their emotional well-being and difficulty coping with stress becomes more challenging. This reinforces the notion that Lazarus and Folkman (1984) noted, namely that using ineffective coping strategies increases emotional difficulties and can increase the risk of mental health problems.

In the study, the regression analysis revealed a significant association between psychiatric disorders and their bio psycho social stressors. The link suggests that emotional or behavioural problems could be triggered by a combination of factors in children and teens, not necessarily one single cause. For many others, mental health problems were related to their own emotional problems, family relationships, social interactions, and inborn predispositions. Tough life events, family pressures, relationship issues and increased emotional sensitivity all contributed to their Psychological distress in many cases. The study also pointed to biological, psychological and social factors as unique combinations with different disorders. This aligns nicely with the George Engel bio-psycho-social model (1977) in which mental health problems develop from the continuous interplay between biology, life experiences and environment.

Mostly anxiety and depression are associated with environmental pressures such as bullying, school stress, parental conflicts, and losses. These findings are supported by a previous study conducted by Deb et al. (2015) who reported that academic pressure, parental expectations, and examination stress significantly contributed to anxiety, and by Patel et al. (2018) who further highlighted that social adversity, interpersonal stress, poverty, and dysfunctional family environments are major contributors to child and adolescent mental health problems. On the other hand, those with OCD and somatoform disorders had greater associations with biologically based factors like genetic risk and brain wiring. These findings are supported by research conducted by Faraone et al. (2005; Stein et al., 2019) who described that abnormalities in cortico-striato-thalamo-cortical pathways and neurotransmitter deregulation are strongly

associated with OCD symptoms. Dissociative symptoms were more likely to be triggered by psychological factors, which included inner emotional turmoil, fear-filled experiences, low self-worth and traumatic memories. Again, these findings are supported by studies conducted by Putnam (1997) and Shonkoff et al. (2012). Children exposed to trauma and chronic emotional adversity often develop dissociative responses as maladaptive coping mechanisms to overwhelming stress." This information is immensely relevant to India's mental health policies, clinical therapies, and school counseling practices. First, the salience of environmental and social stressors puts into sharp focus the need to have systemic school mental health initiatives, emphasizing bullying prevention, emotional resilience, managing stress, and socio-emotional learning. Second, interventions aimed at psycho educating parents and counseling families are also crucial for the management of dysfunctional family systems, poor communication skills and emotional neglect. In conclusion, there is a need for structured coping-skills programs focusing on emotional regulation, problem-solving, being mindful, and coping with stress in an adaptive manner, with our high "frequency pattern" of maladaptive coping styles.

Conclusion

The current study showed that depression and anxiety are the most prevalent reported disorders among the psychiatric childhood population of 8 to 18 years of age, followed by OCD, somatoform and personality issues. Social stresses, maladaptive coping strategies, and psychological vulnerabilities have a significant impact on psychological illnesses among Indian children and adolescents. Social factors that have been identified as major contributors to mental health issues include bullying, familial conflict, academic pressure, maltreatment, and technological addiction. While adaptive problem-solving coping was very rare among individuals, emotional coping and avoidance coping were very common. The sample's primary psychological concerns were anxiety disorders, depressive disorders, behavioral issues, psychosomatic symptoms, obsessive-compulsive symptoms, and trauma-related disorders. The results demonstrate the critical need for early psychological screening programs, school mental health services, parental psycho education, and integrated bio-psycho-social treatments to enhance the mental health of children and adolescents in India.

Limitations of the Study

There are also some limitations in this research; it is a study of psychological problems that are prevalent in children receiving clinical care and these statistics are only applicable to children receiving clinical assistance. Additionally, the cross-sectional design restricts causal interpretation between stressors, coping patterns, and psychiatric conditions. Future research should incorporate longitudinal designs, standardized psychometric measures, and multicentre community samples to better understand developmental trajectories of psychological disorders among youth.

References

- American Psychiatric Association (2022). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed., text rev.; DSM-5-TR). American Psychiatric Publishing.
- Baumrind, D. (1991). The influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, 11(1), 56-95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272431691111004>

- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
- Casey, B. J., Jones, R. M., & Hare, T. A. (2008). The adolescent brain. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1124(1), 111-126. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1440.010>
- Caspi, A., Sugden, K., Moffitt, T. E., Taylor, A., Craig, I. W., Harrington, H., McClay, J., Mill, J., Martin, J., Braithwaite, A., & Poulton, R. (2003). Influence of life stress on depression: Moderation by a polymorphism in the 5-HTT gene. *Science*, 301(5631), 386-389. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1083968>
- Centers for Disease Control & Prevention (2025). *About children's mental health*. <https://www.cdc.gov/children-mental-health/index.html>
- Deb, S., Strodl, E., & Sun, J. (2015). Academic stress, parental pressure, anxiety and mental health among Indian high school students. *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 5(1), 26-34. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijpbs.20150501.04>
- Endler, N. S., & Parker, J. D. A. (1990). *Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations (CISS): Manual*. Multi-Health Systems.
- Engel, G. L. (1977). The need for a new medical model: A challenge for biomedicine. *Science*, 196(4286), 129-136. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.847460>
- Faraone, S. V., Perlis, R. H., Doyle, A. E., Smoller, J. W., Goralnick, J. J., Holmgren, M. A., & Sklar, P. (2005). Molecular genetics of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Biological Psychiatry*, 57(11), 1313-1323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2004.11.024>
- Gururaj, G., Varghese, M., Benegal, V., Rao, G. N., Pathak, K., Singh, L. K., Mehta, R. Y., Ram, D., Shibukumar, T. M., Kokane, A., & NMHS Collaborators Group (2016). *National Mental Health Survey of India, 2015-16: Summary*. National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences, Bengaluru, India.
- Harter, S. (2012). *The construction of the self: Developmental and sociocultural foundations* (2nd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Kessler, R. C., Berglund, P., Demler, O., Jin, R., Merikangas, K. R., & Walters, E. E. (2005). Lifetime prevalence and age-of-onset distributions of DSM-IV disorders in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 62(6), 593-602. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.62.6.593>
- Kolb, B., & Gibb, R. (2011). Brain plasticity and behaviour in the developing brain. *Journal of the Canadian Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 20(4), 265-276.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer Publishing Company.
- McEwen, B. S. (2007). Physiology and neurobiology of stress and adaptation: Central role of the brain. *Physiological Reviews*, 87(3), 873-904. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00041.2006>
- Meaney, M. J. (2010). Epigenetics and the biological definition of gene × environment interactions. *Child Development*, 81(1), 41-79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2009.01381.x>
- Merikangas, K. R., Nakamura, E. F., & Kessler, R. C. (2009). Epidemiology of mental disorders in children and adolescents. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 11(1), 7-20. <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2009.11.1/krmerikangas>
- Nkuba, M., Hermenau, K., Goessmann, K., & Hecker, T. (2018). Mental health problems and their association to violence and maltreatment in a nationally representative sample of Tanzanian secondary school students. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 53(7), 699-707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-018-1511-4>
- Odgers, C. L., & Jensen, M. R. (2020). Annual research review: Adolescent mental health in the digital age: Facts, fears, and future directions. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 61(3), 336-348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.13190>
- Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India (2011). *Census of India 2011: Population composition*. Government of India. <https://censusindia.gov.in>
- Patel, V., Saxena, S., Lund, C., Thornicroft, G., Baingana, F., Bolton, P., Chisholm, D., Collins, P. Y., Cooper, J. L., Eaton, J., Herrman, H., Herzallah, M. M., Huang, Y., Jordans, M. J. D., Kleinman, A., Medina-Mora, M. E., Morgan, E., Niaz, U., Omigbodun, O., & Unützer, J. (2018). The lancet commission on global mental health and sustainable development. *The Lancet*, 392(10157), 1553-1598. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31612-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31612-X)
- Pinquart, M., & Shen, Y. (2011). Behavior problems in children and adolescents with chronic physical illness: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 36(9), 1003-1016. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsr042>
- Plomin, R., DeFries, J. C., Knopik, V. S., & Neiderhiser, J. M. (2016). Top 10 replicated findings from behavioral genetics. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 11(1), 3-23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691615617439>
- Polanczyk, G. V., Salum, G. A., Sugaya, L. S., Caye, A., & Rohde, L. A. (2015). Annual research review: A meta-analysis of the worldwide prevalence of mental disorders in children and adolescents. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 56(3), 345-365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12381>
- Shonkoff, J. P., Garner, A. S., Siegel, B. S., Dobbins, M. I., Earls, M. F., McGuinn, L., Pascoe, J., & Wood, D. L. (2012). The lifelong effects of early childhood adversity and toxic stress. *Pediatrics*, 129(1), e232-e246. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2011-2663>
- Steinberg, L. (2010). A dual systems model of adolescent risk-taking. *Developmental Psychobiology*, 52(3), 216-224. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dev.20445>
- Steinberg, L. (2014). *Age of opportunity: Lessons from the new science of adolescence*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Thapar, A., Cooper, M., Jefferies, R., & Stergiakouli, E. (2013). What causes attention deficit hyperactivity disorder? *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 98(5), 386-389. <https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2012-301691>
- UNICEF (2024). *The state of the world's children 2024*. United Nations Children's Fund.
- World Health Organization (2020). *Adolescent mental health*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health>

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